

**NATIONAL UNIVERSITIES COMMISSION'S
SUPERVISORY ROLE AND INFRASTRUCTURAL
DEVELOPMENT IN SELECTED UNIVERSITIES IN
SOUTH WEST, NIGERIA**

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Makinde Adeboye Abiodun¹
Prof Ngozi Nwogwugwu²
Dr Chibuzor Nwaodike³
Dr Abiola Makinde⁴

¹Department of Business Administration, Babcock University Ilishan, Ogun State, Nigeria. makindeab@babcock.edu.ng

²Dept. of Public Admin. & Political Science, Babcock University Ilishan, Ogun State, Nigeria. nwogwugwu@babcock.edu.ng

³ Dept. of Public Admin. & Political Science, Babcock University Ilishan, Ogun State, Nigeria. nwaodikec@babcock.edu.ng

⁴Human Resources Department, Babcock University Ilishan, Ogun State, Nigeria. makindeb@babcock.edu.ng

**CORRESPONDING
AUTHOR:**

Makinde Adeboye Abiodun
makindeab@babcock.edu.ng

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Abstract

The development of infrastructural facilities in any university environment is fundamental to the attainment of educational goals and objectives that have global impact in this era of modernity. In Nigeria, despite the increasing focus of policymakers on qualitative education and school learning environment, context observation has revealed a dearth of functional infrastructural facilities. This study therefore, examined the supervisory role of National Universities Commission in infrastructural development in selected universities in South-West Nigeria. This study adopted a descriptive research design. The target population were lecturers, students, and NUC officials who have been in their present place of employment who met the inclusion criteria of the study. Data were collected using questionnaire. Data collected were processed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27, and research questions were answered using thematic analysis and inferential statistics of ANOVA and chi-square at 0.05 level of significance. The findings the state of infrastructural development mean score in selected universities in South-West Nigeria was high (academic facilities for students = 3.89; residence and recreational facilities for students = 4.07; and, staff offices and residential facilities = 3.80). The role of NUC in the disbursement of grants to Universities for infrastructural development was good and effective (Chi-Square = 30.94, $p = 0.001$); there is an impact of quality assurance monitoring on maintenance engagement ($f = 7.63$, $p = .006 < .05$); and, NUC's facilities accreditation affected infrastructural development in selected universities in South-West Nigeria ($f = 19.51$, $p = .001 < .05$). In conclusion, the supervisory role of National Universities Commission in infrastructural development is good but not without some hitches. It is recommended that adequate funding should be provided for all tertiary institutions in the country to give them the opportunity of acquiring all necessary facilities, equipment and chemicals for the laboratories for them to scale through the accreditation process rather than resulting to borrowing.

Introduction

Universities are established globally for the noble mandate of achieving the core mission of teaching, learning, researching and community service engagement which are fundamental for national development. Thus, governments, churches and individuals, establish universities not only to train professionals to acquire knowledge for self-development, but also to help discover relevant realities that are useful for the promotion of national growth and development through academic explorations. This has made universities to become modern drivers of knowledge-based economy through its economic development resource and input in production processes (Mense et al., 2018; Odhiambo, 2018). Based on this, universities have taken vantage posture in the scientific modernization and re-engineering advancement in the areas of medicine, physics, agriculture, economics and politics (Al-Youbi, Zahed, Nahas, & Hegazy, 2021).

For instance, no-needle injections, antibodies, atomic scale in metals, measuring distant planets, election swing and other voting trends are some of the scientific milestones that some universities have achieved and recorded in their historical documents (Al-Youbi, Zahed, Nahas, & Hegazy, 2021; Valavanidis & Vlachogianni, 2016). These academic milestones have not only helped to promote the health and wellbeing of people globally, but have also deepened scholars' understanding of the behavioral pattern of some phenomena in the universe. It is in line with the discourse that Ekhosuehi, Iguodala and Osagiede, (2016) commented that the following goals were established to drive higher education to academic excellence:

to contribute to national development through high level relevant manpower training, to develop and inculcate proper values for the survival of the individual and society, to develop the intellectual capability of individuals to understand and appreciate their local and external environment, to acquire both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful members of the society, to promote and encourage scholarship and community service, to forge and cement national unity, understanding and integration (Page 2).

Consequently, universities' stakeholders work assiduously to make sure that basic infrastructures that aid educational goals and objectives are provided so that the universities could be both locally and globally instrumental in modern development.

Infrastructural development involves enhancement of the quality of the various apparatus of infrastructure within a system (Davies et al 2019; Manggat, Zain, & Jamaluddin, 2018). It has been discovered that there are hard and soft infrastructures in any organization. While hard

infrastructure is the physical infrastructure that is tangible and inform of roads, buildings, laboratories, ICT, water and sanitation, soft infrastructure involves human capital and institutions necessary to maintain a system for the delivery of certain services such as healthcare, financial institutions, offices and regulatory mechanisms (Fung, Garcia-Herrero, Lizaka&Siu, 2005).

In another dimension, infrastructure has also been categorized under physical infrastructure, social infrastructure and digital infrastructure (Davies et al, 2019). Physical infrastructure involves road networks, energy like solar panel and electricity, water such as resource management, treatment and flood prevention. While social infrastructure involves hospitals, emergency services, spot facilities, good transport system, community support, public space, libraries and fair regulations and enforcement, digital infrastructure encompasses communication networks and computing facilities in the organization. Hence, scholars have observed that the level of infrastructural development in any educational environment correlates with the quality of knowledge and academic discoveries within that system (Badu, Kissi, Boateng & Antwi-Afari, 2018; Davies et al 2019). It has also been discovered that high quality infrastructural facilities do not only promote better instruction and improve student outcomes, but also reduce dropout rates (Fagbohunka, 2017; Kapur, 2019). This means that consistent attention should be given to the development of different infrastructure in the universities' system so that it will be able to achieve modern academic feats that have global relevance.

In an educational environment where infrastructure facilities are not developed and maintained, it leads to academic deficiency and low productivity of the entire university (Badu, Kissi, Boateng & Antwi-Afari, 2018). This means that where there are inadequate buildings, classrooms, outdated teaching facilities, poor toilet systems and ill-equipped offices and laboratories that should aid academic programs, the university may not be able to compete favorably with other universities in the world. This is because, the existence of poor infrastructure does not only affect the academic performance of the students negatively but also restrict the ability of the lecturers to break barriers and discover new realities that are novel. The effect of poor infrastructure in educational institution is vividly evident in students' dropout rate, students' movement from one school to another, droves of students travelling overseas for schooling and inability to retain teachers in such schools (Akinkuade & Oredein, 2021; Nyamubi, 2017). Beyond this, a university that finds it difficult to address the problem of poor infrastructure in some areas

can lose accreditation of courses that require such infrastructure to thrive academically in the school.

Over the years, researchers, practitioners and government alike have noted the state of decline in the quality of knowledge and skills produced in the educational system in Nigeria, which some researchers have attributed to lack of the necessary infrastructure within the system (Birabil&Ogeh, 2020; Ogunode, Yiolokun&Akeredolu, 2019; Ogunode&Ahaotu, 2021). Lack of educational infrastructure could pose a major threat to the achievement of educational goals to any educational institution including the universities in Nigeria. Incidentally, a substantial body of research has revealed that most universities in Nigeria are in serious need of adequate infrastructural facilities that can aid competitive academic development (Ebekozi, Aigbavboa&Amadi, 2023; Ogunode, Yiolokun&Akeredolu, 2019; Ojo, 2018; John 2016). In addition, it has been further observed that majorities of infrastructural facilities and laboratory equipment in Nigerian universities are not only outdated but equally in deplorable state due to lack of funding (Isi, 2022; Osunyikanmi, 2018). Some studies carried out in some universities in South-West Nigeria revealed that there are deficiencies in the availability of infrastructural facilities in these universities (Subair, Okotoni, &Adebakin, 2012).

Perhaps, this poor infrastructural development in these universities must have resulted due to lack of funds, enforcement mechanisms and serious monitoring of resources for effective utilization. Certainly, poor infrastructural facilities are setbacks to any educational system. This is because such institution may not have some necessary equipment and facilities that can enhance the skills and knowledge of both the staff and the students within the institutions for academic distinction. In Nigeria, one of the reasons while private universities are thriving is because of loss of confidence in the public universities where there are characteristic of service failure, consistent strikes and breaks in academic calendar (Ogunode, Yiolokun&Akeredolu, 2019). These incessant strikes and breaks in academic calendar may have resulted due to agitations from various quarters in order to improve the infrastructural facilities in the universities' system.

Based on the foregoing, the development and sustainability of the infrastructure in the universities is an enormous task that needs to be handled diligently so that the universities may achieve relevant objectives that are beneficial to their countries. Hence, various countries in the world that have recognized the veritable importance of education to the development of their

economy have instituted some mechanisms to ensure high quality education in their nations. Thus in Nigeria, the Federal government, through the Ministry of Education has saddled the National Universities Commission (NUC) with the responsibility of making sure that the standard of universities that meets global recognition is encouraged and sustained.

Higher Education Regulatory Agency that is government agencies created to ensure high quality education in the Nigerian Universities is the Nigeria Universities Commission (NUC). It was established in 1962 as an advisory agency in the cabinet office to coordinate activities within the federal university system, but in 1974, it became a statutory body which was headed by an Executive Secretary (Adeoti, 2015; Isi, 2022). Currently, NUC is a parastatal within the Federal Ministry of Education that is saddled with the responsibility of supervising the activities of all universities in Nigeria to ensure quality education.

Supervision, as noted by Ogunode and Adanna (2022) is fundamental to the accomplishment of any organization's goals and objective. This is based on the fact that it involves providing a professional counsel and support to the organization or institution for quality service. Hence, the supervisory role of the NUC in the universities is a drive to improving both the academic and environmental quality and standard within the university system in order to produce good products that contribute to the socio-economy and digital modernity of the country.

The supervisory responsibilities of the NUC as noted by Adeoti (2015) are as follows:

Advice executive on the financial needs of universities, coordinate the development of universities in Nigeria, Allocate and disburse federal grants and external aids to universities, Research and advice executive on topics relating to higher education development in Nigeria, advice executive on the creation of degree-granting institutions, advice government on the creation of faculties within Nigerian universities (page 116).

The supervisory role of the NUC over the universities in Nigeria as aforementioned can be grouped into three categories relating to its functions. These groups are advisory function, regulatory function and allocation function. The advisory function of the NUC encompasses its responsibility in giving advice over matters concerning the creation of departments, faculties, degrees and financial needs of the universities. This means that as an agency that interfaces with the government, the NUC discusses universities' issues with the federal government by looking at some challenges and strategies to curbing them in a way to enhance both academic and infrastructural development in the universities (Ogunode&Ahaotu, 2021). Based on the advisory

role of this agency, the federal government approves the establishment and commencement of new universities, new programs and the requisite infrastructure that helps to drive such initiatives to meet international standard.

Furthermore, the regulatory dimension of the supervisory role of the NUC depicts its obligation to ensure quality, minimum standard and development of the universities. Hence, the NUC undertake the responsibility of the general planning of the educational system, putting the necessary mechanisms in place to checkmate and ensure minimum standard within the university education system. This responsibility is carried out through accreditation exercise by ensuring that the relevant infrastructure such as classrooms, laboratories and digital facilities that compliment academic programmes are installed.

The allocation function of the supervisory role of the NUC covers its responsibility in grant approval and external financial support. By this function, the agency statutorily oversees and ensures that the resources/funds that are necessary for the development and sustainability of the universities are disbursed. Notwithstanding, some studies have applauded the supervisory role of the NUC as being effective in the areas of accreditation exercises (Okenjom, Agbo, Onyekachi & Elechi, 2017) while others have questioned its efficacy in ensuring physical, social and digital facilities such as laboratories, structures, water management, hostels and communication technologies (Ogunode, 2020; Ogunode & Adanna, 2022). Hence, this study investigated the effect that National Universities Commission on infrastructural development in selected universities in South-West geo-political zone in Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the state of infrastructural development in selected universities in South-West Nigeria?
2. How effective has been the role of NUC in the disbursement of grants to Universities for infrastructural development in selected Universities in Nigeria?
3. What effect has NUC's Quality Assurance supervisory role on infrastructural development in selected universities in South-West Nigeria?
4. How has NUC's facilities accreditation affected or influenced infrastructural development in selected universities in South-West Nigeria.

Methods

Research Design: A descriptive survey design was adopted for this study as the researchers investigated the effect that National Universities Commission on infrastructural development in selected universities in South-West geo-political zone in Nigeria.

Population: The population of this study comprised all students, non-academic staff, academic staff, and NUC officials who have been in their present place of employment in three selected universities in South-west, Nigeria.

Sample and Sampling Techniques: The sample for this study consisted of 500 respondents. A multi-stage sampling method was used. At the first stage, south west was stratified in six (6) states. From these states three states and three Universities were purposively selected. Thus, Lagos State was purposively selected because one of the first set of State Universities accredited (Lagos State University) is situated in it. In a similar vein, Oyo State was purposively selected because the first Federal University (i.e., University of Ibadan) is located in it. Finally, Ogun State was purposively selected because the first privately-owned university (i.e., Babcock University) is domiciled in it. It is believed that, based on the experiences of the universities in these states, they are appropriate for inclusion in this study, especially because of their decades of active existence. And lastly, simple random sampling technique was used in the selection of all the participants of this study.

Instrumentation: A self-developed instrument named "National Universities Commission on infrastructural development Questionnaire" was utilized in this study. It is a 18 item questionnaire and has 5 point Likert rating scales ranges from (5) Strongly Agree, (4) Agree (3) Partially Agree (2) Disagree (1) Strongly Disagree.. The reliability index is 0.821.

Method of Data Analysis: The four research questions raised in this study were tested using descriptive statistics and Multiple Regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval was sought from Babcock University Health and Research Ethics Committee (BUHREC).

Results

Table 1: Frequency distribution of the study participant

S/N	Demographics	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	Status		
	Students	218	43.6
	Staff (Non-academic)	103	20.6
	Faculty (Academic staff)	179	35.8
	Total	500	100.0
2	Years Spent		
	1-5years	215	43.0
	6-10years	74	14.8
	11-15years	88	17.6
	16years above	123	24.6
Total	500	100.0	
3	University		
	Babcock University	179	35.8
	Lagos State University	160	32.0
	University of Ibadan	161	32.2
	Total	500	100.0

Sources: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1 reveals the status distribution of the respondents. A total of 218 (43.6%) participants were students, 103 (20.6%) respondents non-academic staff, and 179 (35.8%) individuals were academic staff. These findings indicate that the majority of the respondents were the students who were the direct beneficiary of the utilization of infrastructural development and resources at the university. Table also illustrates the distribution of the respondents based on the year spent, with 215 (43%) 1-5 years, 74 (14.8%) 6-10 years, and 123 (24.6%). These results indicate that the majority of participants in the study have 1-5 years. Furthermore, the Table also provides an overview of the respondents' working place or university. It shows that 179 (35.8%) participants were from Babcock University, 160 (32%) respondents were from Lagos State University, and 161 (32.2%) participants were from University of Ibadan. These findings indicate that the largest proportion of respondents were from Babcock University.

Table 2: Information on the state of infrastructural development in selected universities in South-West Nigeria

S/N	Variables	SA	A	PA	D	SD	Mean	SD
		Academic Facilities for Students						
1	Adequate classrooms for students	114 (22.8)	198 (39.6)	110 (22.0)	46 (9.2)	32 (6.4)	3.84	1.14
2	Well-equipped laboratories	132 (26.4)	205 (41.0)	103 (20.6)	46 (9.2)	14 (2.8)	3.92	1.06
3	Effective transportation system	133 (26.6)	135 (27.0)	133 (26.6)	55 (11.0)	44 (8.8)	3.77	1.14
4	Classrooms equipped with modern gadgets, projectors & smart boards	135 (27.0)	137 (27.4)	116 (23.2)	78 (15.6)	34 (6.8)	3.76	1.18
5	Well-equipped library/e-library	124 (24.8)	223 (44.6)	90 (18.0)	51 (10.2)	12 (2.4)	4.30	0.93
6	Strong internet connectivity/ICT and computerized facilities	134 (26.8)	140 (28.0)	127 (25.4)	55 (11.0)	44 (8.8)	3.77	1.19
		Weighted Mean Score = 3.89						
		Residence and Recreational Facilities for Students						
1	Adequate and safe hostels	135 (27.0)	139 (27.8)	116 (23.2)	67 (13.4)	43 (8.6)	4.03	1.12
2	Different but adequate sports facilities	102 (20.4)	137 (27.4)	148 (29.6)	69 (13.8)	44 (8.8)	3.99	1.05
3	Food services/Cafeteria for students	135 (27.0)	139 (27.8)	116 (23.2)	65 (13.0)	45 (9.0)	4.03	1.17
4	Modern and quality medical facilities	142 (28.4)	164 (32.8)	125 (25.0)	43 (8.6)	26 (5.2)	4.34	1.02
5	Modern and effective security facilities	136 (27.2)	150 (30.0)	145 (29.0)	40 (8.0)	29 (5.8)	4.13	1.04
6	Sufficient water supplies to all facilities	124 (24.8)	188 (37.6)	110 (22.0)	40 (8.0)	38 (7.6)	3.88	1.11
		Weighted Mean Score = 4.07						
		Staff Offices and Residential Facilities						
1	Staff accommodation for different categories of workers	104 (20.8)	100 (20.0)	147 (29.4)	85 (17.0)	64 (12.8)	3.47	1.09
2	Adequate offices for staff/faculty	135 (27.0)	135 (27.0)	120 (24.0)	67 (13.4)	43 (8.6)	4.00	1.00
3	Food services/Cafeteria for staff	100 (20.0)	100 (20.0)	127 (25.4)	105 (21.0)	68 (13.6)	3.07	1.21
4	Motorable road networks to all facilities	164 (32.8)	243 (48.6)	70 (14.0)	11 (2.2)	12 (2.4)	4.41	0.83
5	Modern equipment in offices and facilities	112 (22.4)	107 (21.4)	168 (33.6)	69 (13.8)	44 (8.8)	3.96	0.98
6	Toilets/conveniences for staff, students and University guests in all facilities	119 (23.8)	193 (38.6)	110 (22.0)	40 (8.0)	38 (7.6)	3.86	1.26
		Weighted Mean Score = 3.80						

NOTE: (5) is Strongly Agree, (4) Agree (3) Partially Agree (2) Disagree (1) Strongly Disagree.

Decision Rule***1-1.49 = very Low Level; 1.5-2.49 = Low Level; 2.5-3.49 = Moderate Level; 3.5-4.49 = High Level while 4.5-5.0= Very High Level.

The findings in Table 2 revealed that the state of infrastructural development in selected universities in South-West Nigeria in terms of academic facilities for students was found to be high (mean = 3.89 on a scale of 5). This suggests that the respondents perceived the state of infrastructural development in selected universities in South-West Nigeria at a high level, which could be as results of the fact that more higher educational institutions domicile in south-west Nigeria. Among all the measures of the state of infrastructural development, well-equipped library/e-library was considered highest with average mean score of 4.30, well-equipped laboratories (average mean = 3.92), followed by adequate classrooms for students (average mean = 3.84), Strong internet connectivity/ICT and computerized facilities, as well as effective transportation system (average mean=3.77), and Classrooms equipped with modern gadgets, projectors and smart boards (average mean = 3.48).

The residence and recreational facilities for students was found to be high (mean = 4.07 on a scale of 5). This suggests that the respondents perceived that the residence and recreational facilities for students were not just available but good and adequate in the selected universities in South-West Nigeria. Among all the measures of the state of infrastructural development, Modern and quality medical facilities was considered highest with average mean score of 4.34, modern and effective security facilities within the school environment (average mean = 4.13), followed by adequate and safe hostels (average mean = 4.03), food services/cafeteria for students (average mean = 4.03), different but adequate sports facilities (average mean = 3.99), and Sufficient water supplies to all facilities (average mean = 3.88).

The staff offices and residential facilities was found to be high (mean = 3.80 on a scale of 5). This suggests that the respondents perceived that the staff offices and residential facilities good and adequate in the selected universities in South-West Nigeria. Among all the measures of the state of infrastructural development, motorable road networks to all facilities within the campus was considered highest with average mean score of 4.41, adequate offices for staff/faculty (average mean = 4.00), followed by modern equipment in offices and facilities (average mean = 3.96), toilets/conveniences for staff, students and University guests in all facilities (average mean = 3.86), staff accommodation for different categories of workers (average mean = 3.47), and food services/Cafeteria for staff (average mean = 3.07).

However, the thematic analysis from the interviews show that the state of infrastructural

development in Nigerian universities was a recurring theme, with interviewees highlighting funding challenges, inadequate facilities, poor maintenance culture, and land encroachment as major issues affecting infrastructure.

Table 3: Chi-Square Contingency Table on the association between Grant Disbursement Awareness and Perceived Infrastructure Quality

<i>Grant Awareness</i>	<i>Strongly Disagree (1)</i>	<i>Disagree (2)</i>	<i>Neutral (3)</i>	<i>Agree (4)</i>	<i>Strongly Agree (5)</i>	<i>Total</i>
<i>Yes</i>	30	40	100	150	104	424
<i>No</i>	10	20	23	10	13	76
<i>Total</i>	40	60	123	160	117	500

Chi-Square Test Summary

<i>Statistic</i>	<i>Value</i>
<i>Chi-Square</i>	30.94
<i>Degrees of Freedom</i>	4
<i>p-value</i>	< 0.001

Interpretation: The significant p-value indicates a strong association between grant awareness and infrastructure quality.

Based on the research question, the key themes that emerged from the discussions include funding allocation, mismanagement of funds, TETFund intervention, and political influences on disbursement. Below is a thematic analysis with quotations from the transcripts.

Table 4: ANOVA Results for Quality Assurance Monitoring and Maintenance Engagement

<i>Source</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p-value</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	12.34	4	3.09	7.63	0.006
<i>Within Groups</i>	56.78	495	0.11		
<i>Total</i>	69.12	499			

An ANOVA was conducted to examine the impact of Quality Assurance Monitoring on Maintenance Engagement. The significant F-statistic and p-value suggest that QA monitoring has a meaningful impact on maintenance engagement, with higher QA ratings associated with greater maintenance engagement ($f = 7.63, p = .006 < .05$)

Table 5: ANOVA Results for Accreditation vs Maintenance Effectiveness

<i>Source</i>	<i>Sum of Squares</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p-value</i>
<i>Between Groups</i>	35.22	4	8.80	19.51	0.001
<i>Within Groups</i>	198.76	495	0.40		
<i>Total</i>	233.98	499			

An ANOVA was conducted to evaluate the relationship between NUC Accreditation Frequency and Maintenance Unit Effectiveness. Frequent accreditation visits are positively associated with higher maintenance unit effectiveness, as shown by the significant F-statistic.

Discussion

The outcome of the first research question revealed that the state of infrastructural development in selected universities in South-West Nigeria was high. The reason for this result or finding is not farfetched. It could be deduced that NUC in order to ensure better education and convenient learning environment will not approve or accredit any programme in a university without ensuring availability and adequacy of academic facilities for students, especially physical and digital infrastructure. This result is not in tandem with the findings of Ogunode (2020) who carried out a study on the administration of public universities in Nigeria: Problems and solutions using a qualitative research design. His findings revealed that inadequate infrastructural facilities is a very big problem facing the administration of public universities in Nigeria since many public universities in Nigeria do not have adequate infrastructural facilities despite the efforts of NUC. Additionally, the findings of Salisu (2018) in her study revealed that the lack of good buildings or funds to rehabilitate collapsed structures poses threat to the overall performance of the institution, leading to falling standard of education. She observed that higher institutions in Nigeria are bedeviled by poor infrastructural facilities, corruption, poor maintenance culture and inadequate funding.

The outcome of the study revealed that the effect of NUC's Quality assurance supervisory role on infrastructural development in selected universities in South-West Nigeria was good and effective. This quality assurance monitoring has a meaningful impact on maintenance engagement and infrastructural standards. It could be said that positive effects include NUC's role in enforcing

minimum infrastructure standards through licensing and accreditation, its accreditation visits driving infrastructure upgrades, and the fact that TETFund was found to play a significant role in funding infrastructure, NUC on the other hand indirectly ensures compliance through accreditation exercises. This is similar to the observation of Ogunode and Adana (2022) that supervision is key to the actualization of quality education at all levels of the educational system. Supervision is the process that involves providing a piece of professional advice and assistance to an individual or institution to improve the quality of the system. One major objective of supervision in an educational institution is to improve quality and ensure quality standards are maintained with the view of producing qualified products for the socio-economic and technological advancement of the country. This finding lend support from the findings of Adelabu and Bolarinwa (2020) who observed that the NUC has collaborated with telecommunication companies to provide affordable and reliable internet access to universities and their students. This partnership aims to bridge the digital divide and improve the overall digital infrastructure for e-learning. They also noted that the NUC has encouraged universities to establish and maintain digital libraries to provide students and researchers with easy access to electronic resources, research materials and academic databases.

The outcome of this study revealed the relationship between NUC accreditation frequency and maintenance unit effectiveness, and it was established that frequent accreditation visits are positively associated with higher maintenance unit effectiveness. Thus, through its facilities accreditation process, which evaluates the sufficiency of classrooms, labs, libraries, student residence halls, and other essential facilities as part of a university's capacity to provide high-quality education, the National Universities Commission (NUC) plays a crucial role in guaranteeing the development of infrastructure in Nigerian universities. These results are consistent with those of Abubakar (2015), who discovered that NCCE accreditation processes had a major impact on the caliber of curriculum content delivery, instructors' caliber, the physical caliber of facilities, and the quality of instruction in educational institutions located in Nigeria's North-West Geopolitical Zone. These results are also consistent with those of Appolus and Obiweluzor (2021), who discovered that accreditation significantly affects the quality of higher education in Nigeria. They also showed that some universities plagiarize staff and equipment from other institutions in order to obtain high accreditation scores that are not maintained, and that accreditation visits significantly improved facilities and library holdings.

Conclusion

It is a common knowledge that universities are compelled to work, repair, and make functional all facilities and equipments in readiness for accreditation. Without accreditation exercise, very few universities would have taken purchases, repairs, maintenance of facilities in the universities. This is a great plus for NUC. In making the exercise more effective, all direct recipients of the facilities should be encouraged to write on the adequacies or inadequacies of the facilities in the universities, the functional and the non functional equipments in the system. My definition of recipients include ASUU, NASU, NANS. A reporting format can be developed by NUC while the feedback is done online to an address given by NUC. These feedback are given to the team leader to verify, ascertain the authenticity of the claim even as they do their normal exercise.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and challenges that were revealed in this study, the following recommendations are hereby proffered:

1. On the part of the regulatory agencies (NUC, NCCE and NBTE), effort should be made to ensure that adequate and appropriate allowance is awarded and paid to the accreditation team/panel members with other necessary logistics to prevent them from taking monetary gift-back from the management of the institution visited.
2. The Nigerian Government should ensure that the allocation of financial resources in Tertiary Educational Institutions is based on the quality of research and the number of students.
3. The government should develop a realistic tertiary education data-bank as this will help for adequate planning and funding of this level of education, for its success will serve as a buffer for the development of the whole economy

Conflicts of Interest

The authors have disclosed no conflicts of interest.

Author's Affiliation

Enock Oluwadare AJIBADE, Ph.D

Department of Religious Studies, Faculty of Arts,
Federal University Oye-Ekiti, Ekiti-State, Nigeria

enock.ajibade@fuoye.edu.ng

<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-3164-3887>

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